

PROVISION OF THERAPEUTIC DENTAL CARE AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES DURING PREGNANCY

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Abstract. This article describes how the etiopathological processes associated with dental disease occur in the prenatal period, the factors influencing the dental status of pregnant women. The clinical features of dental diseases depending on the period and nature of pregnancy were studied. The article discusses the prevalence and intensity of caries and periodontal disease during pregnancy. The scheme of dental examination and clinical examination of pregnant women is given. According to our study, the prevalence of caries and dental diseases in Samarkand currently reaches 75-90% among pregnant women, which indicates that women do not have sufficient knowledge on the prevention of dental diseases. A scheme of therapeutic and prophylactic measures was proposed, based on a review of recent scientific publications designed to improve dental health during pregnancy, antenatal prevention of dental caries in children using endogenous and exogenous means, prevention and treatment methods.

Keywords: pregnancy, caries, tooth extraction, surface caries, dental care.

ОКАЗАНИЕ ЛЕЧЕБНОЙ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ И ПРОФИЛАКТИЧЕСКИХ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ ВО ВРЕМЯ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ

Аннотация. В данной статье описано, как этиопатологические процессы, связанные со стоматологическими заболеваниями, протекают во внутриутробном периоде, факторы, влияющие на стоматологический статус беременных. Изучены клинические особенности стоматологических заболеваний в зависимости от срока и характера беременности. В статье обсуждаются распространенность и интенсивность кариеса и заболеваний пародонта при беременности. Приведена схема стоматологического осмотра и диспансеризации беременных. По данным нашего исследования, распространенность кариеса и стоматологических заболеваний в Самарканде в настоящее время достигает 75-90% среди беременных женщин, что свидетельствует о недостаточности знаний женщин по профилактике стоматологических заболеваний. Предложена схема лечебно-профилактических мероприятий, основанная на обзоре последних научных публикаций, направленных на оздоровление зубов при беременности, антенатальную профилактику кариеса зубов у детей эндогенными и экзогенными средствами, методы профилактики и лечения.

Ключевые слова: беременность, кариес, удаление зубов, поверхностный кариес, стоматологическая помощь.

INTRODUCTION

Provision of dental assistance during pregnancy one of the problems of modern dental science. According to many scientific studies, during pregnancy neurohormonal changes associated with the process of gestation, significantly intensify the development caries. It is known that caries is a polyetiological process. He is essentially associated with the destruction of

calcium hydroxyapatite crystals in tooth tissues. According to the library, rendering dental care during pregnancy should cover everything trimesters of pregnancy. Rendering dental care includes mandatory sanitation of the oral cavity, revision of carious cavities, identification the number of carious teeth and periodontal diseases. It is important to define the index carious process, including number of carious, filled and extracted teeth.

Objectives. Providing therapeutic dental care to pregnant women and strengthening its preventive measures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

On the physiological and pathological course of pregnancy, 30 pregnant women were examined, of which 10 (33.3%) women had a physiological condition, 20 (66.7%) pregnancy pathology: 12 (40%) of them. early toxicosis of pregnant women, 18 (60%) risk of pregnancy was detected. All pregnant women were examined for oral caries and changes in periodontal tissue. The pH of the saliva was studied, microbiological examination of the oral cavity, the study of the condition of the fetus and placenta by ultrasound, dental care at fetal heart rate in cardiopographic examination. Biophysicist A.M. The dynamics of the study was studied by Vinizellos (1983), in which the stress-free test performance of the respiratory function was assessed using fetal tone, amniotic fluid volume, and placental location (according to ultrasound) using the following scores.

- 12-10 points, normal pregnancy;
- 9-8 points - satisfactory;
- 7-6 points - the boundary line;
- 5-4 points - unsatisfactory;
- Less than 4 points - critical.

Periodontal status was assessed as follows:

- examination of bleeding;
- the presence of bleeding gums;
- Presence of gum hyperemia;
- presence of gum pockets > 4 mm;
- Inflammation of periodontal tissue < 3 mm;
- Inflammation of periodontal tissue > 3 mm;
- Determining the distance between the cement-enamel compound and the gums pockets

mm.

Cytology was also performed and the oral cavity underwent cytochemical examination. To do this, parametric and non-parametric data were entered for processing statistical data using the computer program Statgraph.

RESULTS

The study examined the condition of pregnant women, complaints, hemodynamic indicators of pregnant women, as well as the condition of the fetus, uterine contractile activity, fetal heart rate and motor dental care in fetal activity before and after the exchange of experience. The obtained results were statistically processed. Checking the condition of the oral cavity is done during early pregnancy. Treatment of the caries process began after 12 weeks of gestation. The study concluded that the biophysical profile of the fetus before rendering constituted dental care confirms that the condition of the fetus after treatment of the carious process is three long-term at the same time in the process of dental care, teeth with caries

mandatory position of the pregnant woman in the dental chair, tension, restriction of movement helped pregnant women increase uterine and motor tone until the end of fetal activity (through 6-12 hours after dental care).

DISCUSSION

Thus, the provision of dental care to pregnant women included adherence to the following principles:

- knowledge of the characteristics of the course of pregnancy;
- compliance with indications and contraindications in the provision of dental help in the treatment of caries;
- carrying out dental care, taking into account the condition of the fetus and the contractile activity of the uterus;
- the appointment of antispasmodics and sedatives for 30-60 minutes before visiting the dentist;
- compliance with the duration of the provision no more dental care 25–30 minutes;
- when providing dental care in the treatment of 1–2 teeth superficially or 1 tooth with deep caries;
- obligatory daily cleaning teeth with a toothbrush, regardless of the condition of the fetus;
- refusal to take vasoconstrictors preparations for extraction of teeth.

CONCLUSIONS

Compliance with these principles will help maintain the health of the pregnant woman, prolongation of gestation and the birth of a full-term and healthy fetus.

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